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Nod2 controls development of cardiovascular disease at the organismal level through specific gene regulation of FTO.

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We describe here control of the *FTO* locus by NOD2. FTO execution and orchestration of cellular tasks important for foam cell biology and cardiovascular health like LDL receptor uptake by *PCSK9* and a microsomal function involving *MGST1* imparted upon NOD2 the ability to control development of cardiovascular disease at the organismal level.

1 **Results**

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3 Datasets: GSE130350

4 n=3 GFP control; ovarian cancer cells

5 n=3 FTO ectopic expression; ovarian cancer cells.

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7 1. FTO is a major NOD2 molecular target in human cells.

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9 2. FTO controls microsomal molecule MGST1, described for its role in fatty acid biosynthesis and protection of lipids from lipid peroxidation.

10 Ectopic expression of FTO in human cells resulted in robust activation of MGST1.

11 3. MGLL, a lipase enzyme, is a second major target of FTO.

12 A major function of MGLL is catabolism (breakdown) of triacylglycerides.

13 4. FTO negatively regulates the cholesterol biosynthetic enzyme, reductase enzyme *DHCR24*, responsible for converting desmosterol to cholesterol.

14 LDL uptake and accumulation in the foam cell in the coronary arteries is required for atheroma plaque formation.

15 5. FTO controls expression of the major known uptake receptor for low density lipoprotein, the LDL-R uptake molecule PCSK9.

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Citations

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